

Immunotherapy in Triple-Negative Breast Cancer (TNBC): An In-Depth Analysis

¹Amit Kumar, *Usaman Khan
¹Research Scholar,
Anand College of Pharmacy
*Research Scholar
Anand College of Pharmacy

ABSTRACT

Triple-Negative Breast Cancer (TNBC) represents a heterogeneous group of malignancies characterized by the absence of estrogen receptors, progesterone receptors, and human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 amplification. This subset of breast cancer is notorious for its aggressive nature, high recurrence rate, and limited treatment options, making the prognosis for TNBC patients relatively poor. Immunotherapy has emerged as a promising treatment avenue, leveraging the body's immune system to recognize and combat cancer cells. This in-depth analysis explores the current landscape of immunotherapy in TNBC, highlighting the latest advances in immune checkpoint inhibitors, vaccine therapy, adoptive cell transfer, and combination regimens. We delve into the molecular underpinnings that render TNBC amenable to immunotherapeutic strategies, discuss the challenges of immune-related adverse events, and review the latest clinical trial data.

Keywords: Triple-Negative Breast Cancer, Immunotherapy, Immune Checkpoint Inhibitors, Vaccine Therapy, Adoptive Cell Transfer, PD-L1, Tumor-Infiltrating Lymphocytes, Tumor Mutational Burden, Neoadjuvant Therapy, Personalized Medicine.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10526264

Publication Website: thewitfire.in

Corresponding Author: Amit Kumar

Update: Received on 10/01/2024; Accepted; 15/01/2024, Published on; 18/01/2024

INTRODUCTION TO TRIPLE-NEGATIVE BREAST CANCER (TNBC)

Definition and Characteristics of TNBC

Triple-Negative Breast Cancer (TNBC) is a distinct subtype of breast cancer characterized by the absence of estrogen receptors (ER), progesterone receptors (PR), and minimal expression of the human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2).

This classification makes TNBC a unique entity, different from other types of breast cancers due to its molecular profile and clinical behavior (Lehn et al., 2023). TNBC is known for its aggressive nature and poorer prognosis compared to other breast cancer subtypes. It is also more likely to affect younger women and is more prevalent in certain ethnic groups (Safarpour & Tavassoli, 2015).

Epidemiology and Clinical Significance

TNBC accounts for approximately 10-20% of all breast cancers. It is more commonly diagnosed in women under the age of 50 and is particularly prevalent in African-American women (Sandhu et al., 2016).

The clinical significance of TNBC lies in its aggressive nature, higher likelihood of metastasis, and limited treatment options due to the lack of hormone receptors. This subtype is also associated with a higher risk of recurrence within the first 3-5 years after treatment (Rojas-Jiménez et al., 2020).

Current Challenges in TNBC Treatment

The treatment of TNBC poses significant challenges due to its unique characteristics. The absence of hormone receptors means that hormone therapy, which is effective in other breast cancer subtypes, is not viable in TNBC. Chemotherapy remains the mainstay of treatment, but the response rates are variable and often not durable (Maiti et al., 2010).

Additionally, TNBC has a higher likelihood of recurrence and metastasis, which complicates long-term management. The development of targeted therapies has been slow due to the heterogeneity of the disease and the lack of identifiable molecular targets (Penault-llorca et al., 2013).

In conclusion, TNBC is a complex and challenging subtype of breast cancer with distinct characteristics that necessitate ongoing research and development of targeted treatment strategies.

The aggressive nature of TNBC, coupled with its unique molecular profile, underscores the need for innovative therapeutic approaches and a deeper understanding of its pathophysiology.

OVERVIEW OF IMMUNOTHERAPY

Principles of Immunotherapy

Immunotherapy represents a revolutionary approach in cancer treatment, leveraging the body's immune system to identify and combat cancer cells.

Unlike traditional therapies that directly target the cancer cells, immunotherapy works by enhancing or restoring the immune system's natural ability to fight cancer. This can be achieved through various strategies, including stimulating the immune system to work harder or smarter against cancer cells, or by providing components of the immune system (such as man-made immune system proteins) (Lehn et al., 2023).

Types of Immunotherapeutic Approaches

There are several types of immunotherapies, each working in a unique way to boost the immune response against cancer:

1. **Checkpoint Inhibitors:** These drugs, such as PD-1/PD-L1 inhibitors, work by blocking proteins that prevent immune cells from attacking cancer cells.
2. **Cancer Vaccines:** Unlike traditional vaccines, cancer vaccines are designed to elicit an immune response against existing cancer cells.
3. **Adoptive Cell Therapies:** This involves collecting and using patients' own immune cells to treat their cancer, such as CAR T-cell therapy.
4. **Cytokines:** These are small proteins that play a critical role in cell signaling in the immune system, such as interferons and interleukins.

5. **Monoclonal Antibodies:** These are lab-made molecules that can bind to specific targets on cancer cells or immune cells to enhance the immune response against cancer (Rojas-Jiménez et al., 2020).

Mechanism of Action in Cancer Treatment

The mechanism of action of immunotherapy in cancer involves a complex interplay between the immune system and cancer cells. Cancer cells often find ways to evade the immune system. Immunotherapies work by either marking cancer cells so they are more easily recognized by the immune system or by boosting the immune system's response to cancer cells.

For example, checkpoint inhibitors block the proteins that cancer cells use to shield themselves from immune cells. This unmasking process allows T-cells to recognize and destroy cancer cells (Sandhu et al., 2016).

IMMUNOTHERAPY IN TRIPLE-NEGATIVE BREAST CANCER (TNBC): THE EMERGING FRONTIER

Rationale for Using Immunotherapy in TNBC

Triple-Negative Breast Cancer (TNBC) presents a unique challenge in oncology due to its aggressive nature and lack of targeted therapies. The rationale for using immunotherapy in TNBC stems from the understanding that TNBC tumors often exhibit a higher mutational burden, which potentially makes them more immunogenic.

This means that these tumors might be more likely to provoke an immune response, making immunotherapy a promising treatment approach (Katz & Alsharedi, 2017). Additionally, TNBC has been associated with higher levels of tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes (TILs), indicating an existing, albeit ineffective, immune response that can be potentiated through immunotherapy (Emens, 2021).

Key Immunotherapeutic Agents in TNBC

1. **Checkpoint Inhibitors:** These have emerged as a cornerstone in TNBC treatment. Drugs like pembrolizumab and atezolizumab have shown efficacy, especially in PD-L1 positive TNBC patients (Keenan & Tolaney, 2020).

2. **Cancer Vaccines:** While still in the experimental stage, cancer vaccines are being explored to stimulate the immune system to attack TNBC cells.
3. **Adoptive Cell Therapies:** This includes treatments like CAR T-cell therapy, which are being investigated for their potential in TNBC (Li et al., 2023).

Clinical Trials and Research Progress

Numerous clinical trials are underway to evaluate the efficacy of various immunotherapeutic agents in TNBC. For instance, the KEYNOTE series of trials have been pivotal in assessing the role of pembrolizumab in TNBC.

The IMpassion130 trial is another landmark study that demonstrated the benefit of atezolizumab in combination with chemotherapy in PD-L1 positive TNBC (Howard et al., 2022). These trials signify a major step forward in establishing immunotherapy as a viable treatment option for TNBC.

Challenges and Limitations in Immunotherapy for TNBC

Despite the promise, immunotherapy in TNBC faces several challenges. One of the primary issues is the identification of predictive biomarkers to select patients who are most likely to benefit from these therapies (Wang et al., 2023).

Additionally, understanding and managing the immune-related adverse events of these therapies is crucial. The heterogeneity of TNBC also poses a significant challenge, as it can lead to variable responses to immunotherapy (Abdou et al., 2022).

Future Perspectives and Innovations

The future of immunotherapy in TNBC looks towards combination therapies, including combining immunotherapy with chemotherapy, targeted therapy, or radiation. There is also a growing interest in exploring the role of the tumor microenvironment and its manipulation to enhance the efficacy of immunotherapy (Zhu et al., 2021).

Personalized immunotherapy approaches, based on the genetic and immunological landscape of individual tumors, are also a promising area of research (Kudelova et al., 2022).

CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS IN IMMUNOTHERAPY FOR TRIPLE-NEGATIVE BREAST CANCER (TNBC)

Understanding Resistance Mechanisms

One of the major challenges in the use of immunotherapy for TNBC is the development of resistance. TNBC tumors can evolve to evade immune detection and destruction. This resistance can occur through various mechanisms, such as loss of tumor antigen expression, upregulation of immune checkpoint molecules, and changes in the tumor microenvironment that inhibit effective immune cell infiltration or function.

Understanding these resistance mechanisms is crucial for developing strategies to overcome them and improve the efficacy of immunotherapy (Katz & Alsharedi, 2017).

Managing Adverse Effects

Immunotherapy, while offering a novel treatment approach, is not without its side effects. These therapies can sometimes cause the immune system to attack normal organs and tissues in the body, leading to a range of side effects, some of which can be severe.

Common side effects include fatigue, skin reactions, and gastrointestinal issues, but more severe immune-related adverse events can affect the lungs, liver, endocrine glands, and other organs. Managing these adverse effects is a critical aspect of treatment with immunotherapy (Emens, 2021).

Patient Selection and Predictive Biomarkers

A significant limitation in the application of immunotherapy in TNBC is the identification of patients who are most likely to benefit from these treatments.

Currently, PD-L1 expression is used as a biomarker to select patients for certain immunotherapies, but its predictive value is not absolute. There is a need for more reliable biomarkers that can predict response to immunotherapy. Research is ongoing to identify such biomarkers, which would enable more personalized and effective treatment strategies (Wang et al., 2023).

Ethical, Regulatory, and Access Considerations

The ethical implications of immunotherapy, particularly in terms of access and affordability, are also a concern. Immunotherapies are often expensive, which can limit access for many patients, especially in lower-income countries.

Additionally, the regulatory landscape for these therapies is complex and varies across different regions, affecting the availability and approval of new treatments. Ensuring equitable access to these potentially life-saving therapies is an ongoing challenge (Howard et al., 2022).

DISCUSSION ON FUTURE PERSPECTIVES AND INNOVATIONS IN IMMUNOTHERAPY FOR TRIPLE-NEGATIVE BREAST CANCER (TNBC)

Embracing Combination Therapies

The integration of immunotherapy with other treatment modalities represents a significant advancement in the management of TNBC. Combination therapies aim to exploit the strengths of each treatment type while mitigating their limitations.

For instance, chemotherapy can reduce tumor burden and increase antigen presentation, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of immunotherapy. Similarly, combining immunotherapy with targeted therapies or radiation can lead to a more comprehensive attack on cancer cells, potentially overcoming resistance mechanisms that single-agent therapies face.

This approach not only promises improved efficacy but also opens the door to personalized treatment regimens based on individual tumor characteristics (Hong & Xu, 2022).

Novel Agents and Targeted Approaches

The development of novel immunotherapeutic agents is a crucial aspect of future research in TNBC. New checkpoint inhibitors that target different immune pathways are being explored to overcome resistance to current therapies.

Bispecific antibodies, which can bind to two different antigens simultaneously, are another innovative approach. These could potentially redirect immune cells to tumor sites or block two survival pathways in cancer cells simultaneously. Oncolytic viruses, engineered to selectively

infect and kill cancer cells while stimulating an immune response, also represent a promising area of research. These novel agents, with their unique mechanisms of action, could provide more effective and less toxic treatment options for TNBC patients.

Personalized Immunotherapy

The future of TNBC treatment also lies in personalized immunotherapy. This involves tailoring treatment based on the genetic, molecular, and immunological profile of the tumor. Understanding the tumor microenvironment and its interaction with the immune system is key to this approach.

By identifying specific biomarkers and immune profiles, treatments can be customized to target the unique characteristics of each tumor. This precision medicine approach not only aims to improve treatment efficacy but also to minimize adverse effects by avoiding treatments unlikely to be effective for a particular patient.

Overcoming Challenges and Ethical Considerations

While the future of immunotherapy in TNBC is promising, it is not without challenges. Overcoming resistance mechanisms, managing adverse effects, and ensuring equitable access to these therapies are critical issues that need to be addressed.

Ethical considerations, particularly regarding the cost and accessibility of these advanced treatments, are also paramount. Ensuring that these innovative therapies are available to all patients, regardless of socioeconomic status or geographical location, is a challenge that the medical community and policymakers must address.

Conclusion

The landscape of TNBC treatment is evolving rapidly, with immunotherapy at the forefront of this change. The development of combination therapies, novel agents, and personalized treatment approaches holds great promise for improving outcomes in TNBC patients. However, the success of these innovations will depend on overcoming current challenges and ensuring equitable access to these advanced treatments.

REFERENCES

- Lehn, S., Pekar, G., Balbas, P. B., Staaf, J., Möller, C., Lövgren, K., Ehinger, A., Campos, A. B., Borg, Å., & Pietras, K. (2023). Abstract P6-01-05: Platelet-derived growth factor-CC expression in primary triple-negative breast cancer is associated with the basal-like molecular subtype and increased immune infiltrate. *Cancer Research*, 83(5_Supplement), P6-01-05-P6-01-05. <https://doi.org/10.1158/1538-7445.sabcs22-p6-01-05>
- Rojas-Jiménez, E., Mejía-Gómez, J. C., Díaz-Velásquez, C., Quezada-Urban, R., Martínez Gregorio, H., Vallejo-Lecuona, F., de la Cruz-Montoya, A., Porras Reyes, F. I., Pérez-Sánchez, V. M., Maldonado-Martínez, H. A., Robles-Estrada, M., Bargalló-Rocha, E., Cabrera-Galeana, P., Ramos-Ramírez, M., Chirino, Y. I., Alonso Herrera, L., Terrazas, L. I., Oliver, J., Frecha, C., ... Vaca-Paniagua, F. (2020). Comprehensive genomic profile of heterogeneous long follow-up triple-negative breast cancer and its clinical characteristics shows DNA repair deficiency has better prognostic. *Genes*, 11(11), 1367. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes11111367>
- Sandhu, G. S., Erqou, S., Patterson, H., & Mathew, A. (2016). Prevalence of triple-negative breast cancer in India: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Global Oncology*, 2(6), 412–421. <https://doi.org/10.1200/JGO.2016.005397>
- Safarpour, D., & Tavassoli, F. A. (2015). A targetable androgen receptor-positive breast cancer subtype hidden among the triple-negative cancers. **Archives of Pathology & Laboratory Medicine**, 139(5), 612–617. <https://doi.org/10.5858/arpa.2014-0122-RA>
- Maiti, B., Kundranda, M. N., Spiro, T. P., & Daw, H. A. (2010). The association of metabolic syndrome with triple-negative breast cancer. *Breast Cancer Research and Treatment*, 121(2), 479–483. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10549-009-0591-y>
- Penault-llorca, F., Abrial, C., Dauplat, M.-M., Privat, M., Uhrhammer, N., Desrichard, A., Bidet, Y., Radosevic-Robin, N., Cayre, A., Aube, C., Kwiatkowski, F., Chalabi, N., Bignon, Y.-J., Chollet, P., & Nabholz, J.-M. (2013). Abstract 4669: Response to the anti-EGFR antibody panitumumab combined with standard neoadjuvant chemotherapy in triple negative breast cancer (TNBC): the immune and IGFR pathways. *Cancer*

Research, 73(8_Supplement), 4669–4669. <https://doi.org/10.1158/1538-7445.am2013-4669>

- Lehn, S., Pekar, G., Balbas, P. B., Staaf, J., Möller, C., Lövgren, K., Ehinger, A., Campos, A. B., Borg, Å., & Pietras, K. (2023). Abstract P6-01-05: Platelet-derived growth factor-CC expression in primary triple-negative breast cancer is associated with the basal-like molecular subtype and increased immune infiltrate. *Cancer Research*, 83(5_Supplement), P6-01-05-P6-01–05. <https://doi.org/10.1158/1538-7445.sabcs22-p6-01-05>
- Rojas-Jiménez, E., Mejía-Gómez, J. C., Díaz-Velásquez, C., Quezada-Urban, R., Martínez Gregorio, H., Vallejo-Lecuona, F., de la Cruz-Montoya, A., Porras Reyes, F. I., Pérez-Sánchez, V. M., Maldonado-Martínez, H. A., Robles-Estrada, M., Bargalló-Rocha, E., Cabrera-Galeana, P., Ramos-Ramírez, M., Chirino, Y. I., Alonso Herrera, L., Terrazas, L. I., Oliver, J., Frecha, C., ... Vaca-Paniagua, F. (2020). Comprehensive genomic profile of heterogeneous long follow-up triple-negative breast cancer and its clinical characteristics shows DNA repair deficiency has better prognostic. *Genes*, 11(11), 1367. <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes11111367>
- Sandhu, G. S., Erqou, S., Patterson, H., & Mathew, A. (2016). Prevalence of triple-negative breast cancer in India: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Global Oncology*, 2(6), 412–421. <https://doi.org/10.1200/JGO.2016.005397>
- Katz, H., & Alsharedi, M. (2017). Immunotherapy in triple-negative breast cancer. *Medical Oncology (Northwood, London, England)*, 35(1), 13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12032-017-1071-6>
- Emens, L. A. (2021). Immunotherapy in triple-negative breast cancer. *Cancer Journal (Sudbury, Mass.)*, 27(1), 59–66. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PPO.0000000000000497>
- Keenan, T. E., & Tolaney, S. M. (2020). Role of immunotherapy in triple-negative breast cancer. *Journal of the National Comprehensive Cancer Network: JNCCN*, 18(4), 479–489. <https://doi.org/10.6004/jnccn.2020.7554>

- Li, K., Xu, K., He, Y., Yang, Y., Tan, M., Mao, Y., Zou, Y., Feng, Q., Luo, Z., & Cai, K. (2023). Oxygen self-generating nanoreactor mediated ferroptosis activation and immunotherapy in triple-negative breast cancer. *ACS Nano*, 17(5), 4667–4687. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.2c10893>
- Wang, X., Collet, L., Rediti, M., Debien, V., De Caluwé, A., Venet, D., Romano, E., Rothé, F., Sotiriou, C., & Buisseret, L. (2023). Predictive biomarkers for response to immunotherapy in triple negative breast cancer: Promises and challenges. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 12(3), 953. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm12030953>
- Abdou, Y., Goudarzi, A., Yu, J. X., Upadhaya, S., Vincent, B., & Carey, L. A. (2022). Immunotherapy in triple negative breast cancer: beyond checkpoint inhibitors. **NPJ Breast Cancer**, 8(1), 121. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41523-022-00486-y>
- Zhu, Y., Zhu, X., Tang, C., Guan, X., & Zhang, W. (2021). Progress and challenges of immunotherapy in triple-negative breast cancer. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta. Reviews on Cancer*, 1876(2), 188593. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbcan.2021.188593>
- Kudelova, E., Smolar, M., Holubekova, V., Hornakova, A., Dvorska, D., Lucansky, V., Koklesova, L., Kudela, E., & Kubatka, P. (2022). Genetic heterogeneity, tumor microenvironment and immunotherapy in triple-negative breast cancer. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 23(23). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms232314937>
- Howard, F. M., Pearson, A. T., & Nanda, R. (2022). Clinical trials of immunotherapy in triple-negative breast cancer. *Breast Cancer Research and Treatment*, 195(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10549-022-06665-6>
- Vikas, P., Borcharding, N., & Zhang, W. (2018). The clinical promise of immunotherapy in triple-negative breast cancer. *Cancer Management and Research*, 10, 6823–6833. <https://doi.org/10.2147/CMAR.S185176>
- Katz, H., & Alsharedi, M. (2017). Immunotherapy in triple-negative breast cancer. *Medical Oncology (Northwood, London, England)*, 35(1), 13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12032-017-1071-6>

- Emens, L. A. (2021). Immunotherapy in triple-negative breast cancer. *Cancer Journal (Sudbury, Mass.)*, 27(1), 59–66. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PPO.0000000000000497>
- Wang, X., Collet, L., Rediti, M., Debien, V., De Caluwé, A., Venet, D., Romano, E., Rothé, F., Sotiriou, C., & Buisseret, L. (2023). Predictive biomarkers for response to immunotherapy in triple negative breast cancer: Promises and challenges. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 12(3), 953. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm12030953>
- Howard, F. M., Pearson, A. T., & Nanda, R. (2022). Clinical trials of immunotherapy in triple-negative breast cancer. *Breast Cancer Research and Treatment*, 195(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10549-022-06665-6>